

M4.1 Technology & ELSI compliance check: Reach an ELSI compliant federated access model on selected interoperable national data sets

Milestone:

Lead Participant:

CSC

Author:

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Due:

30 Nov 2021

Date Of Completion:

27/9/2023

Means of Verification

[Technology and ELSI compliance check document](#)

Milestone Delayed (if yes, please explain)

Yes. Proof of Concept iterations, incorporating feedback, were used to perform the technology and ELSI compliance check.

Project participants & others

WPs 2, 3, 4
1+MG WGs 2 - 5
CSC, UU, CNAG

Next action steps

Continue the Data Protection by Design and Default analysis of the PoC within the Genomic Data Infrastructure project Starter Kit to ensure that the proposed infrastructure is ELSI compliant.

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